

NAVIGATING THE DUAL ROLES: UNDERSTANDING THE UNIQUE CHALLENGES OF STUDENT-MOTHERS IN PURSUIT OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10634332>

Abstract:

This research delves into the experiences of student-mothers pursuing higher education, uncovering the challenges they face, strategies they employ, and insights gained. This qualitative phenomenological research explores student-mothers' experiences and how they adapt to the changing demands of higher education. This study highlights the complex issues faced by student-mothers, their coping mechanisms and insights gained, by thoroughly examining key informant interviews. Student-mothers navigate the complex dual roles of being both students and mothers, contending with the daily hassles, hard work, constant pressure, and a distinct sense of difference compared to full-time learners. These challenges are compounded by the demands of motherhood, resulting in absenteeism from classes, difficulty focusing on academic tasks, time management struggles, fatigue, and a shortage of time for their children. To cope, student-mothers utilize strategies such as effective time management, seeking understanding from instructors, self-motivation, and financial management. Further, they gain insights into the importance of diligent work in balancing their roles, imparting the value of education to their children, and the belief that they can achieve their goals through hard work. This study's findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the unique experiences of student-mothers, informing the development of support systems and policies to enhance their educational journey and outcomes.

Keywords: *Student-mothers, higher education, phenomenological, challenges, strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Education, acknowledged as a fundamental element of individual development, serves as a source of inspiration and growth. Despite the recognition of education as a right for women, the dual roles of motherhood and student-hood present a significant dilemma for student-mothers, potentially pulling them in conflicting directions (Behboodi, 2017). This challenge is further exacerbated when a woman's commitment to her studies contrasts with societal expectations of her traditional role as a mother, posing a complex interplay of academic operations and challenging competitions. The responsibilities of motherhood place a substantial burden on student-mothers, and in the university context, the simultaneous pursuit of motherhood and studies is often perceived as unconventional.

Despite the recognition of the challenges faced by student-mothers, a research gap persists in understanding the nuanced experiences and impacts of managing dual roles in higher education. Existing studies have identified economic difficulties and time allocation challenges faced by single mothers in Israel (Talman, 2010) and emphasized the positive relationship between support for college student-mothers and the likelihood of university completion in the Philippines (Manalang, 2015; Bullecer and Yang, 2016; Cabaguing, 2017). However, there remains a need for a more comprehensive exploration of the lived experiences and coping mechanisms of student-mothers, particularly in the context of managing the tensions between their roles as students and mothers. This research seeks to bridge this gap by delving into the specific challenges faced by student-mothers pursuing higher education, offering a nuanced understanding of how these challenges impact their daily lives and academic endeavors.

The relevance, necessity, and urgency of this research lie in the need to raise awareness in the higher education sector regarding the gender-specific difficulties encountered by student-mothers. As student-mothers strive to fulfill their dual roles, it is imperative to provide them with targeted assistance and educational support to facilitate their graduation (Manalang, 2015; Bullecer and Yang, 2016; Cabaguing, 2017). By addressing this gap in understanding, the research contributes to the development of informed policies and support mechanisms that can enhance the inclusivity and success of student-mothers in higher education. This study holds significance for academic institutions, policymakers, and practitioners seeking to create a more supportive and equitable environment for student-mothers.

Review of Related Literature

Empirical studies within higher education primarily concentrate on the general student body in regular universities (Eyster, Callan, & Adams, 2014; Beeler, 2016), largely overlooking the distinct challenges faced by student mothers in these environments (Bruenong, Argo, Payne-Sturges, & Laska, 2017). Despite education being recognized as pivotal for empowerment and development (Esia-Donkoh, 2014), the inherent reproductive responsibilities of women often impede some students from reaching their

academic potential. The pursuit of higher education annually by numerous students is essential for societal advancement (Cabaguing, 2017). Nonetheless, as noted by Baum, Ma, and Payea (2010), while higher education generally augments earning potential and satisfaction, this may not hold true for women balancing academia and motherhood. Particularly, female students with children face enduring pressures from educational institutions and their families (Cabaguing, 2017), leading to an elevated risk of non-completion of their studies, as emphasized by Cabaguing (2017). This heightened risk stems from the guilt experienced by student mothers who struggle to balance their roles, fostering a sense of inadequacy in both spheres. The challenge of harmonizing academic commitments with motherhood responsibilities results in feelings of inadequacy as students, evident in subpar academic performance. This detailed examination of the hurdles faced by student mothers within academia contributes to a deeper understanding of their challenges, necessitating tailored interventions and support systems to enhance their academic success.

College Mothers in the Dual role of student and parent. Student mothers recommended a child friendly space in higher institutions, offering priority over others before and after school care, counseling and sharing sessions among student mothers and teachers and leniency is needed for student mothers in relation to study commitments. Ricco, Sabet, & Clough (2009) examined the effect of college mothers towards their children's attitude to school. The study focused on children between 7-14 years with 89 participants between 23-54 years of age and assessed the self-regulation, academic achievement motivation and academic self-efficacy. One teacher suggested that student mothers might be better teachers as a result of being parents, and vice-versa, which echoes findings elsewhere (Ricco, Sabet, & Clough 2008).

Results of this study reveal that being a student mother is difficult to find enough time to navigate between studying and parenting. Lidgard (2004) asserts that significant difficulty for mothers who are students is lack of time to spend with their children, partners, extended families and friends, and to study and complete assignments. Mitchell (2003) argues that unfortunately, as dedicated as single mothers are to both their children and their education, in the end, the time crunch can have devastating effects on the relationship with their children. Students face many challenges during their studies, some of them describe skipping lectures, feel weak, drowsy and lack consideration in classes and one of the students fail her module.

Student Mother Challenges. The decision and commitment to pursue higher education represent one of the most significant undertakings in a student's lifetime. The pressures of family survival and the desire to improve socio-economic status, influenced by parental attitudes towards education, ultimately determine whether a child can remain in school despite the family's limited financial resources (Manalang et al., 2015). Student mothers, as highlighted by Manalang (2015), grapple with managing their dual roles, experiencing challenges such as a lack of time with their baby, skipping classes due to childcare needs, difficulty fulfilling spousal responsibilities, and struggling to establish a close relationship with their child. Additionally, Marandet and Wainwright (2010) noted time as a significant issue for students with dependents, indicating that student mothers often have to sacrifice one role to fulfill another. Smith (2019) discovered in their study

that both pregnant and nursing students faced negative impacts on their studies due to financial difficulties, sometimes needing to miss lectures to seek additional funds or essential materials. Moreover, Najjuma and Kyarugah (2006) found that student mothers contend with the triple roles of productivity, reproduction, and community service, leading to stress, anxiety, and potential health issues. They recommend providing support services such as counseling to help student mothers better manage the challenges they face.

Student Mothers Coping Strategies. Each individual faces various circumstances or events and develops different strategies to overcome them, whether positive or negative, as outlined by Feldman (2005). These responses to challenges are known as stressors, implying that for a student mother, managing stressors becomes a tool for navigating events or circumstances. Affum, Kusi, Mensah, & Afful Broni (2013) indicate that exposure to stressors leads to physiological changes, including increased heart rate and blood pressure, altering skin conductivity. As student mothers confront these challenges, they experience pressure in their functioning, necessitating coping mechanisms to prevent being overwhelmed and failing examinations. Lynch (2008) suggests that student mothers cope with conflicting identities by adopting strategies like material or academic invisibility, balancing academic and maternal roles based on priorities. Studies by Bosch (2013), Ajandi (2011), and Lynch (2008) highlight the need for student mothers to juggle multiple responsibilities and suggest strategies for successful role integration. The success of student mothers hinges on organization and sacrifice across various life domains, requiring meticulous planning and adherence to a strict routine to balance academic pursuits with family responsibilities (Ajandi, 2011).

Research Questions

1. What are the trying experiences of the student-mothers in higher education?
2. How do the student-mothers cope the challenges they have encountered in pursuing higher education?
3. What are the insights gained of the student-mothers in pursuing higher education?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This qualitative study utilized phenomenological approach. It aimed to investigate the experiences of student-mother - how it is to be a student and a mother at the same time. A qualitative research study according to Mills and Birks (2014), aimed to examine a Phenomena that impact on the lived reality of individuals or groups in a particular cultural or social context. Phenomenology aimed to accurately describe the phenomenon without a pre-existing knowledge to a framework, but remaining truth to the facts (Groenewald, 2004). The researcher found this method most applicable to the inquiry in order to provide a comprehensive analysis on the lived experiences of student-mothers.

Research Participants.

The participants of this research study were from the Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology- Trento Satellite Campus (ASSCAT-TSC) from first year to fourth year students in any department. There were five participants who undertake the In-Depth Interview (IDI). Participants were identified using purposive sampling and guided by the following criteria: (a) bonafied student of ASSCAT-TSC; (b) a student-mother ages 22-35; (c) a mother of a child/children ages 1-5 years old; (d) she had the custody of the child; (e) either a fulltime or part time worker; (f) willing to participate in this study. According to a research by Erickson (1982), children under the age of five years need more attention from their mothers specially to grow and develop well psychosocially. Much has been written specifically about role conflict in student parents, and the ways they manage academic, familial, and professional responsibilities when they are 'time-poor' (Moreau and Kerner, 2015). Time spent on childcare is the primary reason for this difference (Wladis et al., 2018). On qualitative studies, Malterud et al., (2016) recommends a sample size of about 5-50 participants. These recommendations helped a researcher estimate how many participants they needed, but ultimately, the required number of participants should depend on when saturation is reached. Hence, these participants were not forced to answer but voluntarily submit their self to become a subject of this study in order to share their experiences on these phenomena.

Research Instruments

A researcher-made interview guide was used in which the interviewer does not strictly follow a formalized list of questions. Instead, he asked more open-ended questions, allowing for a discussion with the interviewee rather than a straightforward question and answer format. This was validated by the English language experts. The participants answered using their language preferences in such a way that they expressed their experiences. The researcher translated the responses in English language and transcribe in accordance with the research standard and ethics.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed and classified thematically. Each problem mentioned is classified in the tables consisting of themes, codes, sub-codes, and the frequency of answers. To demonstrate the detailed analysis of the results, extracts from the students' answers and interviews were transcribed and presented.

RESULTS

Experiences as a Student-Mother in Pursuing Higher Education.

In the pursuit of higher education, student-mothers navigate a complex landscape marked by distinctive challenges, as reflected in the recurrent themes of hassle, difficulty, pressure, and a divergent experience compared to full-time learners.

Strategies used to cope with the challenges encountered in pursuing higher education.

Efficiently navigating the challenges of pursuing higher education as a student-mother necessitates the adoption of strategic coping mechanisms, as elucidated by the identified themes of time management, seeking consideration from instructors, self-motivation, and financial management.

Insights gained in pursuing higher education.

Navigating the dual roles of being both a student and a parent poses considerable challenges, as highlighted by Fernando (2019). Balancing academic responsibilities with parenting duties is a formidable task, with time constraints emerging as a prominent hurdle for participants.

DISCUSSION

Experiences as a Student-Mother in Pursuing Higher Education.

The participants vividly articulated the multifaceted nature of their experiences, underscoring the inherent hassles and hardships inherent in balancing the dual roles of a student and a mother. Egenti and Omoruyi (2011) expound on the stress and trauma endured by student mothers, encompassing psychological, emotional, and physical strains that can adversely impact their well-being and academic endeavors. The identified challenges extend beyond academic pressures, with some grappling with pregnancy, nursing newborns during their studies, and facing the additional burdens of domestic responsibilities. These stressors often lead to a heightened risk of program dropout, exam failures, and compromised learning outcomes. The study emphasizes the unique difficulties encountered by student-mothers, shedding light on the urgent need for tailored support mechanisms within academic institutions to enhance their resilience and academic success. This comprehensive understanding contributes substantively to the

scholarly discourse on the distinct experiences of student-mothers pursuing higher education, offering valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers.

Strategies used to cope with the challenges encountered in pursuing higher education.

Recognizing the critical role of time management, Cabaguing (2017) emphasizes its significance in balancing the multifaceted roles of student mothers, echoing North's (2004) definition that underscores the organization of tasks and events. Achunine (2004) further refines this concept, framing time management as the effective and efficient utilization of time to achieve organizational and personal goals. Additionally, participants in the study highlight the importance of seeking consideration from instructors as a coping strategy, supported by Kelly's (2019) assertion that fostering student success should be a priority for instructors. The impact of instructor support is particularly crucial for student mothers, providing them with the flexibility needed to overcome challenges. Furthermore, self-motivation emerges as a potent coping strategy, as student mothers draw on intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors, as outlined by Lei (2010). The hope of providing a brighter future for their children and fulfilling personal dreams serves as a driving force for student mothers, demonstrating the intricate interplay of intrinsic and extrinsic motivations in their pursuit of higher education. This comprehensive understanding of coping strategies contributes valuable insights to the discourse on student-mother experiences in academia, offering practical implications for both educators and policymakers.

Insights gained in pursuing higher education.

Despite the difficulty, effective time management emerges as a crucial insight, as revealed in the study, emphasizing the participants' dedication to pursuing higher education despite the demanding circumstances. The prevailing ideologies surrounding providing the best for one's child across various developmental dimensions, as discussed by Budds et al. (2017), underscore the importance of education. The study echoes the notion that studying hard not only benefits personal development but also imparts the value of education to children. Acknowledging the potential for learning the hard way, as indicated by one participant, aligns with Bosch's (2013) findings that education significantly impacts various facets of a woman's life. The study emphasizes the participants' resilience, underscored by advanced organizational and time management skills, often supported by their partners. Moreover, the pursuit of higher education is portrayed as a pathway to personal achievement and a better future for their children. The participants express a belief that goals can be attained through hard work, resonating with the concept of self-efficacy discussed by Hassankhani et al. (2015) and Ghasem and Hosein-chari (2013). This strong sense of self-efficacy not only facilitates performance but also empowers individuals to confront and resist failure. Ultimately, the study participants emphasize the indispensable role of education in shaping a better future, aligning with the societal impact highlighted by Esia-Donkoh (2014) and Adofo (2013).

The pursuit of education is positioned as a catalyst for societal development, emphasizing the pivotal role of women's participation in education. This research, encapsulating the intricate interplay between education, parenthood, and personal growth, contributes valuable insights that are relevant for both academic discourse and practical applications.

Conclusions

The present study delves into the multifaceted experiences of student mothers in higher education, shedding light on their challenges, strategies, and gained insights. The primary conclusion drawn from the findings is that student mothers grapple with time management difficulties, with the dual responsibilities of parenthood and academics often conflicting. The study underscores the reciprocal impact on parent and student roles, emphasizing the need for external support to alleviate the burdens faced by student mothers. Despite the inherent challenges, the research reveals that student mothers exhibit resilience and a capacity to learn from their situations. Coping strategies, such as seeking inspiration from their children, praying, maintaining a positive mindset, and disregarding negativity, emerged as crucial mechanisms for overcoming challenges. The study's implications extend to the realm of higher education administration, urging the design of policies that accommodate the unique needs of student mothers and shift the onus of meeting academic standards onto institutions. Additionally, recommendations are made to government entities, specifically the Department of Social Welfare and Development and the Commission on Higher Education, advocating for scholarship grants, financial assistance, and targeted seminars on time management for student mothers, thereby offering practical support to enhance their academic journey. These conclusions present a comprehensive perspective that contributes to the ongoing discourse on the challenges and support mechanisms essential for the success of student mothers in higher education.

Recommendations

Experiences as a Student-Mother in Pursuing Higher Education. As pointed out by the participant, the experiences encountered by the student-mothers in pursuing higher education are hassle, hard, pressured, and different experienced compared to full time learners. Student mothers find that their greatest challenge in adjusting to college life and succeeding in the classroom is acknowledging the pressure. Student mothers deal with the additional issues of childcare, family, and home responsibilities. When evaluating their schedule, or how they spend their time, they also need to consider their goals and priorities. What is most important in their lives right now is their family, friends, school, hobbies, or other activities.

Strategies used to cope with the challenges encountered in pursuing higher education. The strategies used to cope with the challenges in pursuing higher education are time management, ask consideration from instructors, self-motivation, and financial management. Student mothers must set goals to focus on one task, and sometimes student mothers' experience in pursuing higher education is more on time-management

and balancing. Time management plays a major role in helping achieve work-life balance and how to manage the time of being a mother and student. Furthermore, proper time management and balancing must apply, be realistic and must focus on one subject at a time.

Insights gained in pursuing higher education. The insights gained by student-mothers in pursuing higher education are work the class activities on time, study hard for children to see the value of education, one can also learn the hard way, one can reach his goal if he will work hard for it, and education is essential for a better future. One of the result in the study claimed that education is an essential for a better future, in this theme it shows how the student mother see and value the education as a better future for everyone no matter how hard the situation comes in their life.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

A primary consideration in any research study is to conduct the research in an ethical manner, letting the community know that one's purpose for observing is to document their activities. While there may be instances where covert observation methods might be appropriate, these situations are few and are suspect. DeWALT, DeWALT, and WAYLAND (1998) advise the researcher to take some of the field notes publicly to reinforce that what the researcher is doing is collecting data for research purposes. When the researcher meets community members for the first time, he/she should be sure to inform them of the purpose for being there, sharing sufficient information with them about the research topic that their questions about the research and the researcher's presence there are put to rest. This means that one is constantly introducing oneself as a researcher.

Another ethical responsibility is to preserve the anonymity of the participants in the final write-up and in field notes to prevent their identification, should the field notes be subpoenaed for inspection. Individual identities must be described in ways that community members will not be able to identify the participants. The researcher also provided or sent an informed consent letter to the participants before they will be interviewed, and they never been harassed or forced to answer.

Acknowledgments

. The researchers has taken efforts in this study. However, this study would not have been possible without the support and help of many individuals who endeavored big contribution to finish this task.

Agusan del Sur State College of Agriculture and Technology – Trento External Studies Center Colleagues, Friends, Relatives, and former College Classmates, who in several ways supported and encouraged the researcher to complete this undertaking;

Most beloved family of the researcher for the unconditional love, incessant moral support, unending guidance, and unselfish support both morally and financially; and

Above all, special thanks to the Almighty God, for the provision and for using these people as instruments for them to accomplish this study. And for giving the intellect, strength, courage, determination, and good health to make all things possible, particularly in the completion and materialization of this research work.

Thank you so much and God bless!

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